

Person Re-identification Using Color Based Feature for Surveillance Application

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, rapid advancement in information and communication technology (ICT) has resulted in ICT being identified as one of the methods to curb the rampant issues in crime rates and social problems. Local authorities have taken the initiative to install CCTV in public places so that CCTV can be used to record events in a region of interest (ROI) and also be used for person re-identification (PRI). PRI is the task of re-identifying an individual in a ROI for a video surveillance system (VSS). This paper describe the development of video based PRI system. The work entails development of two main signal processing algorithm involving static image and dynamic image (video). Static image processing is done to extract color based feature of static image namely, color histogram, RGB mean, maximum and minimum value of color components whereas the video processing part implements frame differencing to extract data from video source. The PRI algorithm involving static images is meant for identifying color of clothes using extracted color based feature whereas the one involving video images addresses the issue in recognizing the person entering, exiting and re-entering a ROI. Results obtained suggested that the developed PRI algorithm for static image (accuracy of 91%) and PRI algorithm for dynamic image performed well when subjected to the task of recognizing the person in a ROI although the algorithm is very preliminary. In conclusion, the developed PRI algorithm is able to perform its task well and thus, proved the effectiveness of the extracted color based features.

Keywords: Person re-identification; video surveillance system; image processing; extract; color based feature

ABSTRAK

Masa kini, perkembangan pesat dalam teknologi maklumat dan komunikasi (ICT) telah menyebabkan ICT dikenal pasti sebagai salah satu kaedah yang dapat membantu dalam membanteras kejadian jenayah dan gejala sosial yang semakin berleluasa. Pihak berkuasa tempatan telah mengambil inisiatif untuk memasang CCTV di merata tempat awam untuk melakukan tugas pemantauan dengan merakam peristiwa dalam kawasan pantauan (ROI) supaya pengecaman semula insan (PSI) dapat dilaksanakan. PSI adalah tugas untuk mengecam semula insan dalam ROI untuk sistem pengawasan video (SPV). Maka, kertas kerja ini bertujuan memperihalkan pembangunan sebuah sistem PSI berasaskan video yang mudah dan berfungsi. Kajian ini meliputi pembangunan 2 algoritma utama pemprosesan isyarat yang melibatkan imej statik dan imej dinamik (iaitu video). Pemprosesan imej statik dilakukan untuk mengekstrak ciri fitur warna (CFW) seperti histogram warna, nilai purata RGB, nilai minimum dan maksima komponen warna RGB manakala, bahagian pemprosesan video melaksanakan pembezaan kerangka untuk mengekstrak data dari sumber video. Algoritma PSI yang melibatkan imej statik adalah untuk mengenal pasti warna baju menggunakan CFW yang tersari manakala algoritma yang memproses imej video pula menangani isu pengecaman individu yang memasuki, keluar dan memasuki semula ROI. Keputusan yang diperoleh menunjukkan algoritma PSI imej statik (dengan kejituan 91%) dan algoritma PSI imej dinamik yang dibangunkan berprestasi baik apabila ditugaskan untuk mengecam individu yang masuk, keluar dan masuk semula ROI walaupun algoritma yang dibangunkan adalah agak asas dan masih di tahap awal. Kesimpulannya, algoritma PSI yang dibangunkan dapat melaksanakan tugasnya dengan baik dan sekali gus membuktikan juga keberkesanan CFW yang disari.

Kata Kunci: Pengecaman semula insan; sistem pengawasan video; pemprosesan imej; mengekstrak; ciri fitur warna

INTRODUCTION

The development of information and communication technology (ICT) is getting more and more advance. This progress has led to the development of various intelligent systems for comfort, protection and safety purpose. For example Intelligent Building Automation System (iBAS), the Smart Surveillance System etc. These systems are developed to facilitate the needs of people who desire a more comfortable standard of living and also to ensure their safety. Nevertheless, crimes rates are also on the rise which involve criminal activities such as theft, rape, murder and snatch theft cases. This is very distressing as the peace and harmony of the society is being threatened. Consequently, it has become necessary to install surveillance system CCTV (Closed Circuit Television) for instance. In Malaysia, to ensure safety on the road, the Malaysian government has implemented the Automated Enforcement System (AES) in highways such as the PLUS highway to detect and record traffic violations which occurs frequently. CCTV surveillance system has been used to identify suspicious behavior as a proactive measure to prevent unwanted incidents (Saad & Hussain 2010) and thus, becomes a necessity to curb crimes.

The typical CCTV system has its' flaws but, a person re-identification (PRI) module can be embedded into this typical CCTV system and making it more intelligent. Using information such as images and videos from CCTV, PRI can be implemented. What is PRI? It is the process of re-identifying an individual in the Region of Interest (ROI). PRI can be executed on individuals within the ROI. There exists different methods of executing PRI. For example, there are PRI that uses biometric features namely iris and facial recognition. However, method using biometric feature is not suitable because the quality of information obtained through CCTV is generally unfavorable since the video image quality has low resolution and leads to less desired results.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Cai, Y. & Pietikainen, M. (2010), PRI means to match observations of the same person across different time and possibly different cameras by comparing individuals with acquired dataset. Basically, PRI is used to identify an individual through a network of cameras which involves the process of comparing features on either a static image or a video. Re-identification through video will be more difficult compared to static image. These days, the surveillance system is widely used in public areas such as airports, train stations, malls, markets, universities and many more due to the increase in crime rates and social problems to ensure the safety of the public. Smart surveillance system has been proven useful for the detection and prevention of crimes and social problems. Re-identification plays a significant role in processing information for analyzing events and activities. In smart surveillance system, information and data are obtained by processing real-time video.

Rapid growth in computing capabilities and vision techniques has led to the development of new approaches like automatic processing of video in surveillance system. The new approaches include processes such as segmentation, object detection and re-identification, and classification so as to automatically match and identify people leaving and entering the monitored areas from different cameras and different location. The typical PRI algorithm takes on the following steps: (i) Extracting features of image which are more accurate, robust and reliable than raw data. (ii) Building descriptors that can distinguish and describe individuals. (iii) Matching individual image with sample individual image obtained from different camera view by measuring similarities between images (S. Gong. Et al. 2014). Modern surveillance system can determine the lighting conditions and position of a person within the same monitored camera. However, in a network of cameras, problems will arise if a person leaves the monitored area (or simply ROI, short for region of interest) of a camera and enters another ROI of a different camera. Such a problem is known as a re-identification issue due to the lack in spatial continuity of information obtained from the ROI from different camera. There are three aspects to consider in addressing the PRI issues. The first aspect is to determine which part should be divided and matched. Secondly, is to generate invariant feature to be matched with the same part and thirdly, to use an appropriate metric to match those features. In this work, the PRI method is designed with the assumption that a person's appearance does not change. With that assumption, the color and texture feature can be used on robust feature of image for PRI (Saad & Hussain 2013).

METHODOLOGY

In this research, PRI algorithm using color based feature in an intelligent surveillance system is done using MATLAB. The main focus of this research is to perform PRI on individual entering, exiting and re-entering the ROI. The first step is the preparation of static images. Static images includes template and sample images. 10 sets of template images

of different color shirt which includes black, blue, green, grey, mint, orange, purple, red, white and yellow are prepared. 100 sets of sample images of different color shirt are prepared as well. Next, the template images are converted into grayscale images. The color histogram of both original and grayscaled template images are plotted and recorded. Other data such as pixel intensity distribution, mean, maximum and minimum RGB values are also obtained. Data obtained are then tabulated so that comparison between sample and template images can be done easily.

The next step is the preparation of dynamic images or videos. The first video begins with an individual wearing red shirt entering, exiting and re-entering the ROI. The second video features an individual wearing green shirt entering, exiting and re-entering the ROI. The third video begins with a person wearing black shirt entering and exiting the ROI followed by a different individual wearing green shirt re-entering the ROI. After the preparation of both static and dynamic images, the PRI algorithm for both static and dynamic image are developed. The PRI algorithm for static image is developed first. The PRI algorithm starts by computing the RGB mean value of every template image. These RGB mean value are tabulated and stored in MATLAB. The RGB mean value of these template images are set to be the reference. A set of sample image is selected out of the 100 sets and the RGB mean value is computed. Next, the comparison of RGB mean values of the selected sample image against the 10 sets of template images is done through looping.

The PRI algorithm for dynamic image begins with the reading of video input. Pre-processing such as frame differencing is performed on the video. Comparison of the first frame with every frame of the video input is carried out to get the Euclidean distance of these frames. The two frames with the biggest difference are selected and a square region is cropped out. The RGB mean values of these two cropped out regions are then compared. Figure 3 shows the flowchart of the PRI algorithm for both static and dynamic image. After the development of the PRI algorithm, the PRI algorithm is tested. For the PRI algorithm of static image, the differences in RGB mean value of sample and template image helps determine the color of sample image based on template image. The smaller the difference in RGB mean value implies that the color of that sample image is that of the template image. A confusion matrix is then performed to determine the performance of the algorithm. Likewise, the PRI algorithm for dynamic image is also tested. The algorithm determines whether the two cropped out region is of the same color using the Euclidean distance of RGB mean value. Figure 1 shows the flowchart of the PRI algorithm for static image whereas Figure 2 shows the flowchart of the PRI algorithm for dynamic image.

Figure 1. Flowchart of PRI algorithm for static image

Figure 2. Flowchart of PRI algorithm for dynamic image

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The PRI algorithm for static image involves the computation of RGB mean values of the template images. All the RGB mean values including the color of the template images are tabulated as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The RGB mean value of all template images

Nilai min R	Nilai min G	Nilai min B	Warna
27.0888	21.3115	24.8004	Black
2.4010	81.9834	169.5670	Blue
1.3132	131.5475	67.7616	Green
202.2819	201.4637	213.5878	Grey
172.6228	231.0176	237.2329	Mint
252.1869	186.0939	117.4623	Orange
96.2094	50.1483	113.2036	Purple
190.5659	1.3030	29.4078	Red
234.8545	231.8801	238.5516	White
251.6358	218.4179	79.3822	Yellow

100 sets of sample images are selected one by one in the algorithm. The algorithm will determines the color of the selected sample image. Figure 3 shows the selected sample image whereas Figure 4 show the result of the PRI algorithm for static image.

Figure 3. Selected sample image

Figure 4. Result of the PRI algorithm for static image

Through data collected after carrying out the PRI algorithm for static image, a confusion matrix is determined to compute True Positive Rate (TPR), False Positive Rate (FPR) and average accuracy of the algorithm. Table 2 shows the confusion matrix of the PRI algorithm for static image. Table 3 shows the TPR, FPR and average accuracy of the PRI algorithm for static image. The average accuracy of the algorithm is 0.91 or simply, 91% accurate.

Table 2. Confusion Matrix of PRI algorithm for static image

		Expected Event		
		Yes	No	
True Eventr	Ada	TP=91	FN=0	91
	Tidak	FP=91	TN=0	9
		100	0	100

Table 3. TPR, FPR and average accuracy of the PRI algorithm for static image

	True Positive Rate (TPR)	False Positive Rate (FPR)	Average Accuracy
Color Indetification	1.00	1.00	0.91

As for the PRI algorithm for dynamic image, the algorithm begins with the reading of video input. Pre-processing such as the frame differencing is performed on the video. Figure 5 shows the video before processing whereas Figure 6 shows the video after pre-processing.

Figure 5. Video input before processing

Figure 6. Video input after pre-processing

Comparison of the first frame and every frame of the video is carried out to get the Euclidean distance of these frames. A graph of differences in frames is then plotted. The two maximum point of the graph or the two frames with the biggest differences are selected and a square region is cropped out from both selected frames. Figure 7 shows the graph of differences in frames with two maximum point selected.

Figure 7. Graph of differences in frames with two maximum point selected

The RGB mean value of the cropped out region of both selected frames are compared. If the differences or the Euclidean distance of both cropped out region are within the acceptable limit, then it is assumed that both cropped out region are of the same color. This will prove that the individual entering, exiting and re-entering the ROI are of the same individual. Figure 8 shows the two cropped out region of both selected frames whereas Figure 9 shows the results of the PRI algorithm for dynamic image.

Figure 8. Two cropped out region of both selected frames

Figure 9. Results of the PRI algorithm for dynamic image

The PRI algorithm successfully determine the shirt color of the sample image and also re-identifies the individual entering, exiting and re-entering the ROI. However, the PRI algorithm has some limitations. The PRI algorithm for static image, if sample image contains a small portion of the individual body part, the computed RGB mean value will be very different due to the additional color of the body part and this causes some error in the results. Likewise, for the video case, if the cropped out region contains a small portion of the individual body part, again error will occur as a result in erroneous computation of the RGB mean value because of the additional color of the body part in the cropped out region.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, the appearance based approach can be adopted to develop a PRI system that uses color based feature such as RGB mean value, RGB maximum and minimum value and color histogram for surveillance application. The developed algorithm is tested using 100 sets of sample images and the average accuracy of the algorithm is 0.91 or 91%. In addition, three different sets of video are used to test for the dynamic PRI and it was able to correctly identify whether the first individual entering and exiting ROI is the same as the second individual re-entering ROI. However, the PRI algorithm is at its infancy and thus, has its limitation. Therefore, further research needs to be done to overcome the limitations and improve the performance of the PRI algorithm so that the algorithm can be implemented for surveillance application. It is advisable to further improve and develop the PRI algorithm using the C# programming language as it is more superior than MATLAB.

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